

Productive, High-Quality, and Adaptive Peach Varieties

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Abstract: *This article discusses the results of biochemical analysis conducted on various peach varieties grown in a collection orchard established in the poor, stony-gravelly soil conditions of the Fergana region. Based on the biochemical indicators that determine the taste and quality of peach fruits, the best varieties identified include the fuzzless peach varieties 'Ifora' and 'White Nectarine', and the fuzzy peach varieties 'Red Moscow' and 'Elberta'.*

Keywords: *peach, biochemical analysis, dry matter, sugar, total acid, vitamin C, nitrate content.*

Introduction. Nowadays, the importance and role of the agricultural sector in ensuring food security for the population are growing day by day. Specifically, it is a critical task to ensure a reliable supply of agricultural products to the population by rationally using available resources and opportunities, and by introducing scientific achievements and advanced practical results into the sector.

According to researchers, the transition to adaptive, integrated horticulture requires the use of new varieties with valuable economic traits in breeding and introduction efforts [1, 2, 3, 4].

The modern concept of horticulture should be based on keeping the demand for varieties at an optimal level in line with new directions in the field [5, 6].

This is because today, maintaining and utilizing plant genetic collections is considered a strategic issue of national importance in every country [7].

Consequently, this creates new demands for varieties and allows for orchards to be renewed with newly developed varieties every 15-17 years [8].

The research conducted at the Fergana branch of the Scientific Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture, and Winemaking, named after academician M. Mirzayev, is also aimed at solving the existing problems in the field. The studies were carried out at the "Fayzobod" station under the research center's supervision.

Research Methodology. The research is being conducted in the collection orchard of the Fergana Scientific-Experimental Station, which is located in low-fertility, stony-gravelly soils. The study focuses on investigating various local and introduced peach varieties from abroad. The research is carried out according to standard methodologies [1].

Research Results and Analysis

The data on productivity, which is considered the most important economically valuable trait of the variety, shows that the varieties tested in our experiment have different potential capacities. It was found

that in 2022, the highest yield among the fuzzless varieties was achieved with 'Lola' (154 centners/hectare), 'Ifora' (170.5 c/ha), and 'Khosiyat' (217.1 c/ha), while among the fuzzy varieties, 'Champion' (170.6 c/ha), 'Elberta' (160 c/ha), and 'Vostok' (155 c/ha) showed the best results (Table 1). In 2023, a general decrease in productivity was observed across all varieties, but the varietal differences between the fuzzless and fuzzy varieties remained mostly unchanged. Specifically, the standard 'Lola' variety yielded 97.6 centners, while the 'Khosiyat' variety produced 137.0 centners, and 'Ifora' yielded 151.5 centners, resulting in an additional yield of 39.4 and 53.9 centners, respectively. Additionally, the 'Zargaldoq' and 'Red Nectarine' varieties produced 6 to 10.8 centners more than the control variant. However, the 'Muyassar' and White Nectarine varieties yielded 8 to 36.3 centners less compared to the 'Lola' variety.

Analysis of the productivity of fuzzy varieties shows that the standard 'Champion' variety had a yield of 125 centners, while all other fuzzy varieties yielded relatively less. The only variety close to the standard yield was 'Elberta,' which produced 122.3 centners. The average two-year results indicate that among fuzzless varieties, 'Ifora' and 'Khosiyat' achieved additional yields of 53.9 and 39.4 centners, respectively. In the remaining fuzzless varieties, the yields were lower compared to the standard, with only the 'Red Nectarine' variety showing a yield close to the standard. Among the fuzzy varieties, the highest yield of 147.8 centners was recorded for 'Champion'.

Table 1. Yield of different peach varieties

№	Variety Name	Yield, hundredweigh/ha			Additional Yield, hundredweigh/ha		
		2022	2023	average	2022	2023	average
Fuzless Varieties							
1	Lola (control)	154	97,6	125,8	0	0	0
2	White Nectarine	110	61,3	85,6	-44	-36,3	-40,2
3	Red Nectarine	135	108,4	121,7	-19	10,8	-4,1
4	Muyassar	147,3	89,6	118,4	-6,7	-8	-7,4
5	Zargaldoq	125	103,6	114,3	-29	6	-11,5
6	Ifora	170,5	151,5	161	16,5	53,9	35,2
7	Khosiyat	217,1	137	177	63,1	39,4	51,2
NCR05-3.7 hundredweigh/ha NCR05-2.9 %							
Fuzzy Varieties							
1	Chempion (control)	170,6	125	147,8	0	0	0
2	Elberta	160	122,3	141,5	-10,6	-2,7	-6,3
3	Start	119	73	96	-51,6	-52	-51,8
4	Vostok	155	101,1	128	-15,6	-23,9	-19,8
5	Red Moscow	140	98,1	119	-30,6	-26,9	-28,8
6	Fig Peach	137,5	66,4	101,9	-33,1	-58,6	-45,9
NCR05-5.2 hundredweigh/ha NCR05-4.3 %							

The yield closest to the standard was observed only in 'Elberta' (141.5 centners), while all other fuzzy varieties had significantly lower yields compared to the standard.

Thus, the research results indicate that the best varieties in terms of yield potential are the fuzzless varieties 'Ifora' and 'Khosiyat,' and among the fuzzy varieties, 'Champion' and 'Elberta' are recommended.

It is well known that one of the important indicators defining fruit quality is its weight. According to data from 2022, the standard fuzzless variety 'Lola' had an average fruit weight of 79.8 grams, while 'Muyassar' (87.3 grams), 'Zargaldoq' (122 grams), and 'Khosiyat' (176 grams) showed significant advantages in this indicator (Table 2).

Among the fuzzless varieties, the lowest weight (66-70 grams) was recorded for 'Red Nectarine' and 'White Nectarine.' In the fuzzy varieties, the 'Champion' variety had the highest average fruit weight (149.8 grams), while all other varieties showed lower values for this indicator.

The yield of the 'Elberta' variety was found to be close to the standard at 138 grams, while the fruit weight of 'Fig Peach' (89.8 grams), 'Start' (103.3 grams), and 'Vostok' (110 grams) was significantly lower compared to the standard variety. In 2023, when productivity decreased compared to the previous year, the weight of a single fruit increased in fuzzless varieties, ranging from 4 grams (for 'Ifora') to 44 grams (for 'Khosiyat'), and in fuzzy varieties, from 3 grams (for 'Start') to 25 grams (for 'Red Moscow'). This indicates that in our experiment, the decrease in productivity led to an increase in the weight of a single fruit.

The external appearance of the fruit is one of the most important indicators determining its quality and competitiveness. In 2023, despite a decrease in overall yield compared to 2022, an improvement in fruit quality indicators was noted. Among the fuzzless varieties, the best external appearances were recorded for 'Muyassar,' 'Ifora,' and 'Khosiyat,' which were rated between 4.2 and 4.8 points. Additionally, 'Lola' (4 points) and White Nectarine (4 points) also received high ratings.

In the fuzzy peach varieties, it can be observed that fruit quality in 2023 has improved compared to the previous year. Notably, the varieties Champion (control), Elberta, Vostok, Fig Peach, and Red Moscow are among the most attractive in appearance, with high ratings of 4 to 4.5 points. The lowest score, 3.5 points, was given to the Start variety. In terms of taste, among the fuzzless varieties, Red Nectarine, White Nectarine, Muyassar, and Ifora were rated highly, with scores of 4 to 4.5 points, while among the fuzzy varieties, the highest rating went to Fig Peach (5 points), followed by Elberta, Champion, Vostok, and Red Moscow (4 to 4.2 points). For overall fruit quality, Muyassar, Ifora, and Khosiyat received the highest ratings, ranging from 4.1 to 4.5 points, while among the fuzzy varieties, Champion, Elberta, and Fig Peach excelled with scores of 4.2 to 4.5 points. Therefore, it can be recommended that the fuzzless varieties Muyassar,

Table 2. Fruit quality of different peach varieties

№	Variety Name	Weight of a Single Fruit, grams		External Appearance (points)		Taste (points)		Sugar Content, %		Overall Quality (points)	
		2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023	2022	2023
Fuzzless											
1	Lola (control)	79,8	87,6	4,2	4	4	3,5	13	10,9	4,1	3,8
2	White Nectarine	66	75	3,5	4	3,6	4	13,5	13,5	3,2	4
3	Red Nectarine	70	84	4	3,5	3,5	4	13,6	10,2	3,7	3,9
4	Muyassar	87,3	98	4	4,2	3,5	4	12,4	13,8	3,7	4,1
5	Zargaldoq	75	88	3	4	3,8	3,5	12,9	12,3	3,5	3,5
6	Ifora	75	79,3	4,2	4,5	4	4,5	14,1	14,2	4	4,5
7	Khosiyat	176	223,5	3,9	4,8	3,5	3,5	13,5	10,6	4,2	4
Fuzzy											
1	Champion (control)	149,8	167,5	4	4	4,2	4,2	13,8	10,4	4,1	4,2
2	Elberta	138	146,5	4	4,5	3,8	4	12,5	13,8	3,9	4,2
3	Start	100,5	103,3	3	3,5	3,2	3,8	11,2	10,2	3,1	3,7
4	Vostok	100	110	3,8	4,2	4	4	13	11,5	3,7	4,1
5	Red Moscow	115,2	140	4	4,5	4,2	4	12,9	11,5	4	4,2
6	Fig Peach	78,6	89,8	3	4,3	4,5	5	15,7	14,0	4,1	4,5

Ifora, and Khosiyat, as well as the fuzzy varieties Champion, Elberta, and Fig Peach, be considered the best in terms of quality indicators.

In the fuzzy peach varieties, it can be observed that fruit quality in 2023 has improved compared to the previous year. Notably, the varieties Champion (control), Elberta, Vostok, Fig Peach, and Red Mockow are among the most attractive in appearance, with high ratings of 4 to 4.5 points. The lowest score, 3.5 points, was given to the Start variety. In terms of taste, among the fuzzless varieties, Red Nectarine, White Nectarine, Muyassar, and Ifora were rated highly, with scores of 4 to 4.5 points, while among the fuzzy varieties, the highest rating went to Fig Peach (5 points), followed by Elberta, Champion, Vostok, and Red Moscow (4 to 4.2 points). For overall fruit quality, Muyassar, Ifora, and Khosiyat received the highest ratings, ranging from 4.1 to 4.5 points, while among the fuzzy varieties, Champion, Elberta, and Fig Peach excelled with scores of 4.2 to 4.5 points. Therefore, it can be recommended that the fuzzless varieties Muyassar, Ifora, and KKhosiyat, as well as the fuzzy varieties Champion, Elberta, and Fig Peach, be considered the best in terms of quality indicators.

In terms of taste, the fuzzless variety Ifora (4.5 points) stood out, while among the fuzzy varieties, Fig Peach (5 points) took the lead. Regarding total sugar content, the fuzzless varieties White Nectarine (13.5%), Muyassar (13.8%), Ifora (14.2%), and the fuzzy varieties Elberta (13.8%) and Fig Peach (14%) recorded the highest levels.

In terms of overall quality indicators, the fuzzless varieties White Nectarine, Muyassar, Ifora, Khosiyat, and the fuzzy varieties Champion, Elberta, Red Moscow, and Fig Peach can be singled out.

It is well known that among the peach varieties grown in orchards, there are no immune or highly resistant varieties to powdery mildew and leaf curl diseases. According to some authors, hybrid varieties obtained by crossing with other stone fruits, which are highly resistant or immune to these diseases, can be included in this category [2]. However, the economic value of hybrid peaches obtained by this method tends to be low.

One of the most damaging diseases affecting peach orchards is leaf curl, caused by a fungus. The fungal spores enter the cracks of twigs and buds, where they overwinter, and in spring, they begin to infect the peach tree leaves. White or brown blisters, which later turn reddish and are covered with a powdery coating, appear on the leaves, marking the onset of leaf curl. The disease also spreads to one- and two-year-old branches as it progresses.

The severity of the disease and resistance levels are assessed according to international standards using a 9-point scale [3]. For example, if 3 points are recorded (11-25% of the plant or leaf surface is affected by the disease), the resistance level to the disease is rated as 5 points.

Research conducted on a collection of 12 peach varieties revealed that none were completely resistant to leaf curl, with all varieties showing varying degrees of infection (Table 3).

Table 3. Degree of peach varieties' leaf curl disease infection

No	Variety Name	Infection (%)				Resistance Level (points)	
		Leaves		Fruits		2022	2023
		2022	2023	2022	2023		
Fuzzy Varieties							
1	Lola (control)						
2	White Nectarine						
3	Red Nectarine						
4	Muyassar						
5	Zargaldok						

6	Ifora						
7	Superlola						
Fuzzless Varieties							
1	Champion (control)						
2	Elberta						
3	Start						
4	Vostok						
5	Red Moscow						
6	Fig Peach						

Furthermore, a two-year analysis showed that in 2022, all varieties were more severely affected by leaf curl.

Specifically, it was found that the fuzzless varieties were more susceptible to the disease compared to the fuzzy ones. For instance, the fuzzless reference variety Lola showed moderate resistance (5 points), with more than 15% of its leaves affected by the disease.

Among the fuzzless varieties, White Nectarine and Red Nectarine were found to be the most affected by the disease, with an infection rate of 29-30%. In 2022, the disease was also observed on the fruits, with fruit infection rates reaching 6-10% in the fuzzless varieties and 4-5% in the fuzzy varieties.

As mentioned earlier, the fuzzy varieties were less affected by leaf curl compared to the fuzzless varieties. This is because none of the fuzzy varieties studied showed a strong susceptibility to the disease.

In 2023, the disease incidence decreased, and no symptoms were observed on the fruits. However, the disease resistance patterns between varieties remained consistent.

The Ifora and Khosiyat varieties demonstrated resistance to the disease, with infection rates of 7-8%, showing stronger resistance compared to the reference variety. Among the fuzzy varieties, the Champion variety, used as a reference, showed less than 11% infection, indicating high resistance to leaf curl. Additionally, the Elberta, Vostok, and Red Moscow varieties were also noted for their high resistance to leaf curl disease.

Based on our research, the fuzzless varieties Ifora and Khosiyat, as well as the fuzzy varieties Elberta, Champion, Vostok, and Red Moscow, are recommended as resistant to leaf curl disease.

Recommendations and Suggestions

For the reconstruction of old, unproductive orchards and the establishment of new ones, it is recommended to use high-yielding, quality fruit-bearing, and disease-resistant fuzzless peach varieties such as 'Ifora' and 'Khosiyat,' as well as fuzzy peach varieties like 'Elberta' and 'Krasnaya Moskva.'

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